

Challenges and Scope of Regression Testing: A Review

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Abstract: Regression is one the most famous problem in the software industry .The process of software development contains many stages. Out of these stages software testing is one of the most important stage in any software development. If program contains any error then it comes in to notice to the development teams in this stage. Addition of new module in the main program takes place in the maintenance stage. Due to addition of new module new test case is created due to which the size of test suite is increased. When any modification is done in the program, testing of this program is carried out. This testing is known as Regression testing. This review paper has focused on regression testing challenges along with scope. The pros and cons of regression techniques have been highlighted. More over the review paper has also introduced some regression testing reduction techniques.

Keywords: Software Testing, White Box Testing, Black Box Testing, Regression Testing

[1] INTRODUCTION

Regression testing is a testing method that is employed when any modification is done in program. In this method examination of modified program with some test cases is done in order to reestablish one confidence that the program can perform according to the specification. In other words we can say that Regression testing is performed on changed programs to produce confidence that modifications are correct and have not adversely affected alternative parts of the program In the development segment, regression testing could initiate after the recognition and rectification of errors in a tested program. A tested program may be a program that has been tested with a top quality test arrange. In the maintenance stage it is considered that regression testing is a major aspect. In the maintenance stage the software may be corrected, adapted to new setting, or increased to enhance its performance. Modifying a program involves making new logic to correct a mistake or to implement a modification and incorporating that logic into an existing program.

A crucial distinction between regression testing and development testing is that in regression testing we tend to sometimes have a longtime suite of tests accessible for use. One regression testing strategy reruns all such tests; however all this retest might consume immoderate time and resources. Another, selective retest, chooses the checks from the recent test suite that are deemed necessary to check the changed program. We tend to run these tests, so if necessary produce new ones, probably to satisfy some coverage criterion. This selective approach is useful given that the price of choosing the check set is a smaller amount than the price of running the tests we tend to are able to omit.

Types of Regression Testing .

1. Progressive Regression Testing:

It involves a changed specification. Whenever new enhancements, or new knowledge necessities square measure incorporated in an exceedingly system, the specification are changed to replicate these additions. In most cases, new modules are other to the software with the consequence that the regression testing method involves testing a changed program against a changed specification.

2. Retest-all regression testing:

This type of testing is very boring and tends to waste a lot of time. In this testing all the features of a particular product as well as reusing all test cases even where the modifications have not been made. If only a small change , has been introduced in the existing product this type of regression testing is not at all advisable

3. Selective regression testing:

It is performed in order to analyze the affect of new code added to the already existing code of the software. In this type of regression testing, a subset from the existing test cases is utilized. It will cut down the effort required for retesting and the cost involved. For example, a test unit is re-run in case when some modification is done in the program entities such as functions and variables.

4. **Corrective Regression Testing:** In corrective regression testing it is not required to change the specification. Only some directions of the program and probably some style choices square measure changed. This has necessary implications as result of most test cases within the previous test arrange square measure seemingly to be valid within the sense that they properly specify the input-output relation. However, due to the modifications to the management and

knowledge flow structures of the software system, some existing test cases are not any longer testing the antecedent targeted program constructs. The corrective regression testing is typically go through as soon as some corrective operation is performed on the software system .

5 Complete regression testing:

When multiple modification is required in the already existing code complete regression testing is considered as the best to be used in case. In addition to this it is particularly used when the new change has certain affect on the root code of the software. Performing this type of testing is extremely beneficial to recognize unpredicted issues. As soon as this testing is concluded, the final system can be made available to the user.

[2]DIFFERENCES BETWEEN TESTING AND REGRESSION TESTING

Regression testing is not equivalent to the testing which is done in the testing phases. There are a lot differences between them.

1. Accessibility of test plan: Testing starts with a specification, an accomplishment of the specification and a test plan with test cases added during the specification, design and coding phases. All these test cases are assumed as fresh because up to this point they have not been put into effect in the program . Perhaps regression testing begins with a modified specification, a customized program and an old test plan which requires updating. All test cases in the test plan were run up to that time and were helpful in testing the program.

2. Purpose of test: The main intention behind testing is to test the accuracy of the program. It also checks the interconnection of the modules in the program. After that it provides the desire result according to the user requirement. Regression testing is concerned with the modification part of the program. Therefore total concentration is given to that part of program which is modified. It is not essential to test all the test cases.

3. Time allocation:

Testing time is generally calculated before the development of a product. This time is higher than the half time which is required for the total product completion time. On the other hand, in the overall product price and program regression testing time, particularly time for corrective regression testing, is not normally included. As a result when regression testing is done, it is nearly always performed in an emergency situation. The tester is normally urged to complete retesting as soon as possible and most often is given limited time to retest.

4. Development information:

In testing, the testing group and development group may be same, they know all about software. If the testing groups are different then the testers can usually

query the developers about any problem in the software. In view of the fact that regression testing may be performed at a time and place where the original developers may be available it is considered that in regression testing, the testers will not be the developers of the product. Therefore it is suggested that all the relevant development information should be stored if regression testing is to be successful.

5Time duration: The time taken for testing is normally more in comparison to the regression testing because testing all parts of a program are covered in comparison to regression testing where only part of a program is covered. Therefore testing needs more time.

[3] LITERATURE REVIEW

However there have been several researches in field of regression testing. Some of them have been represented in this section.

In 2017, A. Ngh, M. Munro [1] provided overview of regression testing.

In 2005, X. Lin [2] introduced Regression Testing in Research And Practice.

In 1997, W. E. Wong, J. R. Horgan, S. London, and H. Agrawal [3] did Study of effective regression testing in practice.

In 1998, T. Y. Chen and M. F. Lau [4] performed simulation study on some heuristics for test suite reduction.

In 2002, B. Vaysburg and L. H. Tahat [5] did dependence Analysis in Reduction of Requirement Based Test Suites.

In 2003, J. A. Jones and M. J. Harrold [6] proposed Test-Suite Reduction and Prioritization for Modified Condition / Decision Coverage.

In 2003, T. Y. Chen and M. F. Lau [7] worked on divide-and-conquer approach in order to perform test suite reduction.

In 2004, M. P. E. Heimdahl and D. George [8] implemented Test-Suite Reduction for Model Based Tests. They discussed Effects on Test Quality and Implications for Testing.

In 2004, T. Xie [9] represented Framework for Detecting Redundant Object-Oriented Unit Tests.

In 2004, J. Black, E. Melachrinoudis [10] proposed Bi-Criteria Models for All-Uses Test Suite Reduction.

In 2005, S. McMaster [11] did research on Call Stack Coverage for Test Suite Reduction.

In 2005 S. Sprenkle [12] introduced empirical comparison of test suite reduction techniques for user-session-based testing of web applications.

[4]MODIFICATION REQUIRED REGRESSION TESTING

There are basically four types of modification in which regression testing is essential.

1 New Functions – The most common reason to run regression tests is adding a new function to software. Whenever a new code is added it is necessary that it has to be fully compatible with the previous one. Before putting the new code developers do not consider its compatibility. They rely on regression testing for identification of problems.

2 New Integration – The second reason for doing regression testing is the assimilation of one product with another. Testing ensures that the two products work as intended after integration.

3 Revised Functions – In some situations, developers need to rectify software for functionality purposes. In these situations, developers might revise existing characteristics while discarding or editing others. It is a possibility that it causes hidden problems. Regression testing ensures the functionality of the remaining product.

4 Bug Fixes – The fourth type of change is when developers fix pre-existing bugs. In some situations it is a possibility that in process of fixing one bug creation of another problem takes place because developers have to change the source code. It is ensured by regression testing that these changes didn't break or change the program. That these changes didn't break or change the program.

[5] STEPS TO PERFORM REGRESSION TESTING

As soon as a modified or new code is written, few steps are needed to take.

Smoke/Sanity Test – First of all do a smoke and sanity test. These tests confirm the programs stability ahead of regression testing. This step is taken in order to ensure that system is stable and it doesn't crash at the time of testing.

Requirements Analysis – After that the code requirements are analyzed. In most of the situations the modification done at last moment will cause bugs. It is necessary to analyze the latest code ahead of adding it, in order to ensure that it meets the users' requirements.

Test Cases for Critical Functions – By observing test cases it is determined that out of the three types of regression testing which one is required. It is required to discover that out of partial, unit, or complete regression testing which is used ahead of starting the testing process. Of the various test cases designed for regression testing, Sanity test cases are considered as one of the most critical for customers and development teams because they test out the basic functionality of the system. After that common setup associated with test cases are checked on priority. The test cases that are considered for regression testing as the software life cycle progresses are then executed, as per bandwidth and requirement. Integration test cases, are specially important because while performing integration testing

a series of regression test cases are considered. An unexpected repair at the last moment, can break the combination between multiple modules, even in an already tested application.

Collection of Test Cases – once the prioritization of the test cases is finished; they can be selected for execution. The choice of these test cases is made principally on the basis of area of frequent defects and based on the characteristic and their necessity. Tests are run aggressively for those units of code that have undergone multiple changes repeatedly.

AI can be employed to run tests on the programs as well, depending upon the company's requirements

[6] CHALLENGES OF REGRESSION TESTING

Common types of challenges which are faced by companies when it comes to regression testing are listed below

It Is Too costly

When a program is tested several times throughout its build or update, it is hard to give explanation for the cost upper-management sometimes. A reasonable concern which is always come in to notice that why should a company test something which is already tested earlier. In some situation there is a possibility that the cost required for testing of an important piece of software is more than the cost of regression testing, especially if the software affects the ability to communicate with customers. It is harmful for sale and reputation as well.

Optimization and Maintenance

As soon as any modification is done it is essential to modify existing regression test suites. For this it is required to add, remove, or edit existing test cases. In regression testing it is essential to do this in a fixed time. If more time is consumed it will add more stress on development teams.

Due to this problem regression tests are not running by many companies but it shouldn't. The time spent optimizing and maintaining suites pales in comparison to the time needed to find and fix software problems after an update.

Time Consuming: A lot of time is taken by regression testing to complete. Regression testing often involves running existing tests again. Therefore testers might not be overly encouraged at having to re-run tests.

Complex: One of the other things which is considered here is that as products get restructured, it becomes quite complex. Due to this the lists of tests in regression pack is also grown to a huge amount.

Disclosing of Business Value: It is ensured by regression testing that existing product characteristics are still in working order. It is very difficult to disclose the value of regression testing to non-technical leaders within the business. It is desired by executives that the product move forward. Therefore a considerable time investment is done in regression testing to ensure that existing functions are working otherwise it is difficult

to put it for sale. Due to this development team and rest of your team might lose access to precious apparatus that affect customer service. A little bit of extra time and energy now could save you money and stress later on.

Regression Testing Best Methods:

While doing regression testing, there are some methods which should be kept in mind.

Repeatedly Updation of Regression Pack: A regression pack is a group of test cases that are performed as each new software update is accomplished. The scripted tests incorporated in a regression pack are produced by keeping in mind the requirement of specifications of older versions of the software. Casual or ad-hoc tests may also be incorporated in the pack. It is a good thought that regression pack should be kept up to date. Regression testing can be time-consuming. At last it is require that thing one should check whether an older feature which has been detached is still working.

Focus on Highly-Trafficked Paths: Highly-trafficked paths are the mainly use cases for application. It will incorporated the fundamental function of application and most popular characteristic. One should know about his core group of users and the characteristic features and interactions they are most dependent on. Tests which ensures that this core functionality is working according to the requirement is also incorporated in regression pack .

Re-Run Successful Test Cases: Tests by which bugs and defects are identified until that time is also incorporated in regression pack. On the other hand, tests that the program passes over and over again are good candidates for archival.

Automate: The process becomes much more efficient with the help of automated regression testing. Testers becoming bored and unmotivated due to the successively use of same tests over and over again. The value of work might suffer as well as motivation dips. With the help of automated regression testing it is possible to free up testers to work on the trickier case specific tests. more boring tests are handled by automation software . One more consideration is also taken here that testing software can be re-used although there is an initial expenditure.

[7] ADVANTAGES OF REGRESSION TESTING

This section has introduced benefits of regression testing.

1) MORE TEST ARE COVERED IN LESS TIME:

A considerable efforts and time is taken by testing to coverage entire software. But, regression testing executes the particular scenarios and provides continuous working. In addition to this, data inputs or devices can be changed on every run.

2) KNOW THE PROBLEMATIC BUGS EARLIER:

Regression testing assist a company by telling it which bug is producing trouble to application following the software changes. It is possible for engineers to modify or replace the application code with the appropriate value to remove the bugs.

3) HIGH-QUALITY SOFTWARE:

System stability is established by Regression testing while enhancing the application continuously. It executes the same steps repeatedly and allows the team with shorter development cycles by establishing the high-quality of software.

4) INCREASE EFFICIENCY AND COST EFFECTIVE:

Due to the computerization of regression test cases it is possible to keep the cost low by minimizing the team and involvement of human interaction. Simultaneously, resources can concentrate more on strategic and important tasks.

5) TIMELY INTERVENTION:

Regression testing provides opportunities to recognize the problematic area in the system. It replace the same with proper programs to improve the processing of the app. Therefore it offers efficacious solutions to the business. Regression testing helps in making a appropriate way to record GUI response as an automated input.

6) SOFTWARE UPGRADE:

Regression testing helps to maintain the technology up-to-date. It is also considered as a long-lasting and provide valuable solution to remain the software for proper usage, and reusable. Such a software testing produces high ROI and it consume less time because the entire testing is processed through automated software.

According to a latest survey which is done by a leading IT giant revealed that around 1000 bugs and technical gnaws were found in 47 different areas. In absence of regression testing, the software' s functionality could have fallen into difficulty.

[8] LIMITATION OF REGRESSION TESTING

The life of the testers becomes easier with the help of regression testing makes because it is working on a large software project. On the other hand, it has some limitations which are listed below.

1. In the absence of automation, it is hard to manage the cost of regression testing as the testing scope grows with every new feature coming to the product.
2. Automating regression needed skilled software engineers.
3. Changes in old features lead to modifications in the related test cases which further requires versioning.
4. Testing new features requires more cases to be added which increases maintenance cost.
5. It impacts the overall cost of the project budget.

6 Regression tests have to run upon any small or big change taking place in the code as the smallest of modifications could bring down the existing functionality.

[9] REGRESSION TESTING REDUCTION TECHNIQUES

A. Genetic Algorithms There are many issues of software testing. These issues are effective creation of test cases, reduction of test case, prioritization of test cases, etc. These issues demand on effort, time and cost of testing. The utilization of evolutionary algorithms for automatic test case production and reduction has become an interest topic for researchers. One example of evolutionary algorithms is Genetic Algorithm (GA). It is computational Intelligence based approach. It is utilized as a solution for the problem of test cases reduction like evolutionary computation. A genetic algorithm is proposed for test-suite reduction which forms the initial population based on test history. It calculates the fitness value with the help of coverage and cost information. After that with the help of genetic operations it selects the successive generations. These steps will be repeated until a minimized test-suite set is not obtain. It is shown by results that the proposed test-suite reduction technique has cost-effectiveness.

B. Requirement Based The main purpose of test suite reduction is to fulfill the testing requirements with a minimum number of test cases. Ahead of generating test cases it is essential and required to optimize testing requirements. Test suite reduction can be solved by testing requirement optimization. With the help of relation graph it is possible to minimize the requirement set by graph contraction. The experiment is formed and enforced with the help of specification-based testing. Testing requirement relation graph is introduced in order to hide the details of testing requirements and test cases and to manage test suite reduction. Some requirement contraction methods are proposed in order to produce a small requirement set. Also, an empirical study on specification-based testing is executed. By the study a comparison is done between the relative effectiveness of testing requirement optimization to test case reduction. In

order to compare with test suite reduction, all test cases of each testing requirement are created. After that the desirous algorithm is applied on the constructed test suites for reduction.

C. Fuzzy logic -With the help of fuzzy logic improvement of test suites can be achieved. It is a safe technique. It can decrease the regression testing size and execution time. Fuzzy logic can be employed in many areas such as communication, bio informatics and experts systems. Quality of testing which can be done with the help of fuzzy logic is based on objective function which is quite similar to human judgment. The attachment of fuzzy logic with genetic algorithm and swarm optimization can be utilized to obtain optimization in test suite for multi-objective selection criteria. Therefore, in aim to discover a test suite that is optimal for multi-objective regression testing one proposed an expert system. It utilize a technique and level of testing based on a defined objective function, similar to human judgment with the help of fuzzy.

D. Clustering When creation of test cases is done, there are many unnecessary test cases with no use. These unnecessary test cases increases the testing effort, cost and time of testing. The time spent in testing can be reduced if the number of test cases is reduced. One can utilize the data mining approach of clustering technique in software testing to reduce the test suite. By the utilization of clustering techniques the number of test cases is reduced. It also helps in the improvement of efficiency of software testing. With the help of clustering the program can be checked with any one of the clustered test cases rather than with the entire test case that is produced by the independent paths

E. Coverage Based - One of the important issue which must be kept in mind during test suite reduction is the coverage aspect. It is ensure by coverage-based reduction techniques that majority of the execution paths of the given program are exercised

Regression testing must sustain the fault detection in addition to minimizing the size and the time of test. In Case Base Reasoning (CBR) there are three cases classifications: case, auxiliary and pivotal case. Case based is Artificial intelligent which search for the most similar problems to solve problems; in this case a memory is needed. Auxiliary case can be deleted without affecting competence, but only reduces the efficiency of the system. On the other hand pivotal cases have a direct effect on the competence of a system if it is deleted. As we said CBR uses path coverage criteria to reduce the redundancy test cases. Path coverage uses a control flow graph which can derived from a source code, path oriented test case generation technique used to derive a test cases from a control flow graph where each state can reveal a fault

F. Program Slicing- This type of method is introduced in order to check a program over a specific

property and to create a slice set It is a set of statements effect to determine a statement. In many situations it is the output statement of a program, based on input values. With the help of slicing techniques it is possible to control flow of a program for each test case. It is also important to specify which statements are invoked with that test case. There are basically three types of slicing techniques which are listed below

- 1 Static slicing
- 2 Dynamic slicing
- 3 Relevant slicing

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